

A STUDY OF EFFECT OF REASONING ABILITY ON READING HABITS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The Presented research paper studies a study of effect of reasoning ability on reading habits of high school students. Random sampling is the method of drawing a portion at population or universe so that all possible samples at fixed size have the same probability of being selected random sampling is free personal biases sampling. In this way 120 Students were selected for the study. Out of the above types of sampling the investigator has selected the sample i.e. random sampling for the research. Random sampling is that method of sampling in which individual of the population has equal chance or probability of selection of individuals for constituting a sample. The individual of a population has equal chance of being picked up into the sample. Total numbers of 120 students were selected in which 60 males and 60 females of High school students were selected. After the administration of the test the investigator has located the scores of each answer sheet and calculated it. The calculation is done is a t- test method. **Result-** There is no significant difference in the reading habit of high school student's of rural and urban school. There will be no significant difference in the Reading Habits of high school students of Rural and Urban school in relation to high reasoning ability. There will be no significant difference in the reading habits of high school students of rural school and urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

Keywords: Genders/Male and Female, Reasoning ability, Reading habits

INTRODUCTION:

“Reasoning is that form of thinking which finds to complete expression in logical forms (whether judgement (the conclusion) is dependent upon other judgement (the premises).” **(English And English 1958)**

All distinguished men have been given to the habit of reasoning and it utterly impossible to arrive at any tolerable degree of distinction without habit. According to **Dewey** (1910) “The presence of doubt and necessity of some sort of discovery is necessary for reasoning.” Every person does reasoning to the stage of his mental development because reasoning is just a kind of thinking and everybody thinks. According to **Dewey** reasoning is undertaken when faced with a complex problem a man's thinking stops man's constructive imagination works. During reasoning efforts are made to understand how situation on the basis of past conception. At the time of reasoning one makes efforts to come to a decision through the scrutiny of the present based on the experience of the past arriving at a decision is the main function of reasoning. **Michal Shemesh** (2006) gender related differences in reasoning skills and learning interests of junior high school students. The purpose of this study was to investigate gender. Related differences in this relationship between the development of formal reasoning skills and learning interests during the early adolescent stage.

“Habit is a flywheel of a society, its nature most precious conserving agent. The great thing then is to make our nervous system our ally instead of our enemy. We must have automatic and habitual as early as

possible, as many useful actions as we can, and guard against growing into ways that are disadvantageous as we guard against plague. The more details of our daily life we can hand over to the effort less custody of automatism, the more our higher power of mind will be set free for their proper work.”**William James (1973)**

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is conducted to see the impact of Reading Habits on reasoning ability of higher secondary students(11th). The study is limited to students of eleventh class only. Here, the researcher is of the opinion that reading habits have significant impact on reasoning ability of higher secondary students (11th). Good Reading Habits helps in developing the overall personality of a student, it opens the path to a new world of knowledge for the student which ultimately help him to decide his career in the future.

Educators have been re-examining the old concepts of individual differences, inheritance of ability, the constancy & reliability of I.Q. measures, & other factors that have long been a part of educational thinking of many civilized countries. Sometimes, teachers come across such students who have above average I.Q. but even then they show poor performance in their examination. After investigation a great number of such students showed faulty reading habits. A proper guidance to them would help in converting these faulty habits of the students into desirable ones, like, better reading speed, correct pronunciation, correct modulation, better vocabulary & so on.

If faulty habits of the students are converted into desirable ones, it will help them is gaining more efficiency, more knowledge of various fields & ultimately may lead to a good direction for their career, i.e. helping them to have a directional. Since reading habit is one of the major factor of learning it is necessary to know how far it is related with the reasoning ability and reading habits of higher secondary students.

Michal Shemesh (2006)- “Gender related differences in reasoning skills and learning interest of junior high school students.” **Rifkin, Teonie, John Harry(1991)**- “Study of science reasoning development in students at river side city college.” The result of the study point to the importance of science in the curriculum and of academic involvement in the sciences for the development of students science reasoning ability. **K.P. Krishna & Vijay Rani Agrawal (1977)** studied the relation between reading habit & maladjustment. **Miller (1971)** studied the relation between the reading habits of the pupils & attention, concentration & anxiety of the pupils. **Datta (1982)** studied reading habits of primary children in context of their socio-economic status. **N.N. Kantawala (1980)** studied reading attitudes of High School Students of Kaira. District. Though number of researcher have been done on reasoning ability of the pupils related to certain variables but not much interest has been shown towards the reading habits & their impact on the reasoning ability of higher secondary students (11th).

Hence, “A Study of Effect of Reasoning ability on reading habits of High School Students.”.is considered to be an important aspect by the investigator for the present study.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY:

Any period of change is likely to be accompanied by many impending difficulties. Adolescent age is a period of transition from childhood which implies numerous developmental changes. According to G S. Hall, it is called this period as a period of stress and strain fraught with many problems but other psychologists have laid emphasis on the cultural conditions as the problem at this age. The present study reveals the major areas of reasoning ability and reading habits of high school students in relation to their gender, habitat and educational stream. As it has known that adolescent is a nation builder of tomorrow. Various changes occur in this period. These changes affect the adjustment process of the adolescent. Another main objective of this study is to understand developmental characteristics, psychological well-being and problems of Adolescent reading and reasoning ability. Every teacher and parent must know about nature and changes emerging in the transition period from childhood to adulthood. They must also know the various problems fraught with developmental characteristics to deal effectively with the problem of adolescents. The study also helps in maintaining the mental health of studtens. The progress of the country depends on the maximum exploitation of its human resources. The sound mind is one of the first requisite conditions of development. The adolescent is marked with a number of problems that affect mental health. The study of 9th grade students is very important in order to

preserve, cure and prevent the incidence of maladjustment.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION:

Gender: Means male and female secondary school Students.

REASONING ABILITY:

Here in this study, reasoning means climax of thinking. Reasoning is the highest form of thinking that needs a well organized rain. In the process of reasoning, the individual reasons from the past known circumstances to the present of future unknown conditions on the basis of past experiences the power of reasoning gradually develop in human beings. In present world people striving to get employment, it is necessary that people should have knowledge of reasoning ability to pass competitive examinations.

Reasoning ability has been operationally defined as the scores obtained by the student in the standardized test of reasoning ability by developed by K. Bayati.

READING HABIT

Reading habits are well-planned and deliberate pattern of study which has attained a form of consistency on the part of students toward understanding academic subjects and passing at examinations. Reading habits determine the academic achievements of students to a great extent.

Reading habit has been operationally defined as the scores obtained by the students in the standardized test of reading habits developed by Dr. Jamuna Lal Bayati measuring eight dimensions of this test (Budgeting time, physical conditions for study reading ability, role taking, factor in learning motivation, memor, taking examination, preparation for examination. Here the investigator is using only the reading ability part.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDIES:

1. To study the reading habits of high school students of rural and urban school
2. To study the reading habits of high school students of rural & urban school in relation to their high reasoning ability.
3. To study the reading habits of high school students of rural & urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀₁ There will be no significant difference in the reading habit of high school students of rural and urban school.

H₀₂ There will be no significant difference in the Reading Habits of high school students of rural and urban school in relation to their high reasoning ability.

H₀₃ There will be no significant difference in the reading habits of high school students of rural and urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

METHOD: The present study Investigator use by Purposive Random sample technique.

SAMPLE:

The primary purpose of research it is to discover principles that have universal application but to study a whole population and to arrive at generalization would be impracticable and not possible also some population is so large that their characteristics cannot be measure fortunately the process of sampling makes it possible to draw valid inferences or generalization on the basic of careful observation of variables with in a relatively small proportion at the population.

A sample is a small proportion of population selected for observation and analysis by observing the characteristics of the sample one can make certain inferences about the characteristics at the population from which it is draw sample are not chosen haphazardly they are chosen in a systematic random way so that the change or the operation at probability can be utilized.

In the present study the different high school of rural and urban were selected purposive randomly and from that the student were selected randomly. By this method the population has an equal and independent chance of being selected in the sample.

According to SAMPSON & KOFKA (1962) : “Population is an aggregate of items processing a common traits or traits.”

Table – 1.1
Table showing school wise population

Types of school No. of school	Rural	Urban School	Total
Existing Schools	05	05	10
Selected under study	03	03	06

Out of 10 schools the investigator has randomly selected 03 Rural and 03 Urban school as population for the present study

SAMPLE

The primary purpose of the research is to discover principles that have universal applications, but to study a whole population and to arrive at generalizations would be impracticable and not possible also. Some populations are so large that their characteristics cannot be measured fortunately, the process of sampling makes it possible to draw valid inferences or generalizations on the basis of careful observations of variables within a relatively small proportion of the population.

According to Calvin, the two major characteristics of good sample are :

- ☒ A good sample must be representative of universe of population.
- ☒ A good sample must be adequate in size in order to be reliable.

It is very expensive and time taking to study the research problem on the whole population. To make the study a reliable and valid it has become necessary to employ the test of the research on a limited and select persons, student or subject which is studied in order to make preferences about the whole population. Our knowledge and attitudes and our actions are based to a very large extent on a sample. Sample are not chosen haphazardly they are not in a systematic random way, so that the chance or the operation of probability can be utilized.

In the survey research, the most fundamental step is the sampling. Sampling is more practical than that of a complete census. It gives more accurate conclusion.

According to Partner (1958) : “An optimum sample in a survey is one which fulfills the requirements of efficiency, representatives, reliability and flexibility”.

For the present study researcher have been selected by purposive random sampling out of the total schools of urban and rural, Approximately 120 High School Students male and female were selected from different schools of Durg block level.

Tools:

The tools used for the present study investigator has adopted Hindi version of reasoning ability test by L.N. Dubey (2012) and Hindi version of reading test by Dr. Jamuna Lal Bayati and Dr Pushpa Sodhi (2013)

Statistics:

After the administration of the test the investigator has located the scores of each answer sheet and calculated it. The calculation is done is a t-test method. The investigator has used the t-test to find out the reading habits of high school students of rural and urban school

Process of Research:

Before in banking on details of research methodology and technique it seems appropriate to present a brief overview of the research process. Research process consists of series of actions or steps necessary to effectively carry out research and the desired sequencing at these steps the chart shown well illustrates a research process.

The chart indicates that the research process consists of a number of closely related activities as shown through 1 to VII but such activities overlap continuously rather than following a strictly prescribed sequence. At times the first step determines the nature of the last step to be under taken.

It subsequent procedures have not been taken account in the early stages; serious difficulties may arise which may even prevent the competition of the study. One should remember that the various steps involved in a research process are not mutually exclusive or their separate and district. They do not necessarily follow each other in any specific order and the researcher had to e constantly anticipating of each step in the research process the requirement of the following order concerning.

Analysis and interpretation:

The parole of analysis in to reduce data in to an interpretable form so that the relation of research proffer can be studied tested. It is throat system systematic analysis that the important characteristics which are hinder is the data are revealed and valid generation in drawn.

After this research has to draw internees form the analysis that he or she has dome this part of investigation which in associated with drawing of inferences form the collected facts after analysis in referred as ‘interpretation of data’ it proved certain conclusion about the problem under study interpretation takes the result of analysis makes intervener pertaining to research relations studied and draws conclusion for this accurate and adequate data must be obtains.

This chapter deals with the finding of the statistical process “A study of effect of reasoning ability on reading habits of High School students”.

At the outset of this chapter, the researcher first tried to find out the difference in the reasoning ability of both Rural and Urban school students of class 9th. With the help of Table 1.1

The results of the t-value for the given hypothesis are as follows :-

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There will be no significant difference in the reading habit of high school students of rural and urban school.

TABLE – 1.1

Reading habits	N	Mean	S.D.	t-Value
Rural School	60	52.55	12.32	1.95
Urban School	60	48.65	9.55	
df = 118		P < 0.05	Not significant	

From the table 1.1 mean and standard deviation of reading habit of high school students of rural school are 52.55 & 12.32 and reading habit of high school students of urban school are 48.65 & 9.55 respectively. The ‘t’ value is found to be 1.95. This value is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. From the result it is inferred that there is no significant difference in the reading habit of high school student’s of rural and urban school.

Thus, the above hypothesis is accepted and there will be no significant difference in the reading habit of high school students of rural and urban school.

Result- There is no significant difference in the reading habit of high school students of rural and urban school.

H₀₂: There will be no significant difference in the Reading Habits of high school students of rural and urban school in relation to their high reasoning ability.

Table 1.2

High reasoning ability	N	Mean	S.D.	t-Value
Rural School	60	45.35	8.45	1.08
Urban School	60	43.25	12.52	
df = 118		P < 0.05	Not-significant	

From the table 1.2 mean and standard deviation of Reading habits of high school students of rural school are 45.35 & 8.45 and Reading habits of high school students of urban school are 43.25 and 12.52 respectively. The 't' value is found 1.08. This value is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. From the result it is inferred that there is no significant difference between the Reading habits of high school students of rural and urban school.

Thus, the above hypothesis is accepted and there will be no significant difference in the Reading Habits of high school students of Rural and Urban school in relation to high reasoning ability.

H₀₃ : There will be no significant difference in the reading habits of high school students of rural and urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

Table 1.3

Low reasoning ability	N	Mean	S.D.	t-Value
Rural School	60	49.33	9.32	0.84
Urban School	60	47.63	12.58	
df = 118		P < 0.05		Not-significant

From the table 1.3 mean and standard deviation of reasoning ability of high school students of rural school are 49.33 & 9.32 and Reading habits of high school students of urban school are 47.63 & 12.58 respectively. The 't' value is found 0.84. This value is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. From the result it is inferred that there is no significant difference between the Reading habits of high school students of rural school and urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

Thus, the above hypothesis is accepted and there will be no significant difference in the reading habits of high school students of rural school and urban school in relation to their low reasoning ability.

Conclusion:

Students are more practical in solving problems and reasoning the things of daily life. In the present world when people are striving to get employment if is necessary that people should have knowledge of reasoning to pass the competitive examinations. Human beings have the ability to reason since birth. The ability to reason varies from individual to individual. The person having more reasoning ability has greater intelligence. A person will be able to deal with the problem by using the reasoning power. An option best suited to their personality and interest. Reading habits plays a vital role in developing a student's attitude towards his future. Which shows that there exist no difference in the habit of reading & reasoning among both rural and urban school students.

Parental background also play a vital role for the development of the students because if the parents or family are well-educated they can emphasized and provide the path for their development because sometimes parental background becomes barrier in the path of the Childs progress. In initial stage they don't knew how to make their child more eligible for the education. So with the help of parental background can play a dominant role for the development of reading habits and reasoning ability of the students?

Educational implication:

Similar Reading Habits Across Rural and Urban Schools

The finding that there is no significant difference in the reading habits of high school students in rural and urban schools has several educational implications:

1. Equal Access to Reading Materials: Despite differences in geographical location, students in both rural and urban schools have similar access to reading materials, which suggests that efforts to provide equal access to educational resources have been successful.
2. Similar Learning Environments: The similarity in reading habits suggests that the learning environments in both rural and urban schools are similar, which implies that teachers and educators in both settings are using similar instructional strategies and materials.

3. Student Motivation and Interest: The finding suggests that student motivation and interest in reading are not influenced by geographical location, which implies that educators can use similar strategies to promote reading motivation and interest in both rural and urban schools.

Implications for Educators and Policymakers

1. Focus on Pedagogy: Educators and policymakers can focus on improving pedagogy and instructional strategies to promote reading habits, rather than worrying about geographical location.
2. Professional Development: Educators in both rural and urban schools can benefit from professional development opportunities that focus on promoting reading habits and improving instructional strategies.
3. Resource Allocation: Policymakers can allocate resources more effectively, focusing on providing equal access to reading materials and promoting reading habits, rather than targeting specific geographical locations.

Future Research Directions

1. Investigating Other Factors: Future research can investigate other factors that influence reading habits, such as socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and access to technology.
2. Comparing Reading Habits Across Different Age Groups: Research can compare reading habits across different age groups, such as elementary, middle, and high school students, to identify patterns and trends.
3. Examining the Impact of Interventions: Researchers can examine the impact of interventions, such as reading programs and literacy initiatives, on reading habits in rural and urban schools.

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